

NanoSolveIT

Innovative Nanoinformatics models and tools: towards
a Solid, verified and Integrated Approach to Predictive (eco)Toxicology

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List of Abbreviations

CC – Coupled Cluster; **CG** – Coarse-Grained; **CBM** – Conduction Band Minimum; **CIF** – Crystallographic information file; **CNTs** – Carbon Nanotubes; **COSMO** – COnductor-like Screening MOdel; **DFT** – Density Functional Theory; **DFTB** – Density Functional Tight Binding; **DOS** – Density of states; **DZP** – Double Zeta plus Polarisation or Double-Z Polarised; **EMMC** – European Materials Modelling Council; **ENM** – Engineered Nanomaterial; **FF** – Force Field; **GFN-FF** – Geometry, Frequency, Non-covalent interaction – Force Field; **GFN-xTB** – Geometry, Frequency, Non-covalent interaction - extended Tight Binding; **GPU** – Graphics Processor Unit; **HF** – Hartree-Fock; **HOMO** – Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital; **IUPAC** – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry; **LUMO** – Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital; **MODA** – Model Oriented Data Analysis; **MD** – Molecular Dynamics; **MIEs** – Molecular Initiating Events; **MP2** – Møller–Plesset second; **NM** – Nanomaterial; **NP** – Nanoparticle; **OSMO** – Ontology for Simulation, Modelling and Optimisation; **PBE** – Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof; **QM** – Quantum Mechanical; **QSAR** – Quantitative Structure- Activity Relationship; **SCC** – Self Consistent Charge; **SCF** – Self Consistent Field; **SIESTA** – Spanish Initiative for Electronic Simulations with Thousands of Atoms; **UCD** – University College Dublin; **VBM** – Valence Band Maximum; **WP** – Work Package

Abstract

This deliverable presents a summary of the methodologies used within NanoSolveIT for computational modelling of electronic and molecular properties of nanomaterials (NM) with electronic structure methods and molecular dynamics, using open-source software with L-GPL3 licence combined with inhouse tools and scripts.

Efficient modelling of NMs was achieved with tested methodologies for intrinsic property calculations that produce results with electronic and atomic resolution in a fast manner applicable to a broad range of systems. Here we present full details of the developed and tested models, including their complete documentation using MODA templates. The libraries of associated descriptors are also described, which can be built upon for further predictive modelling and computational analysis and are available through nanoPharos database. The described work was done by the teams of UTARTU, SU, NovaM (also Jan Gerit Brandenburg), and UCD.

Methodology of calculation of intrinsic descriptors of nanomaterials

1. Introduction

Nanomaterials (NMs) are characterised by their physicochemical properties, which are often classified as intrinsic (not affected by the NMs' surroundings) or extrinsic where the specific property is dynamic and depends on the nature and composition of the surrounding environment. Experimental data are commonly used to create or determine if there is a relationship between the biological activity of NMs and their physicochemical properties [1-6]. Importantly, the toxicity of NMs is often found to be related to their molecular and electronic properties, especially those determining the interactions with biological entities including proteins, biomolecules and cellular receptors [1-6]. Therefore, the key to effectively constructing predictive models and exploring their environmental dependence is access to physicochemical properties of NMs through theoretical calculations [1-7], e.g., atomistic scale materials modelling to complement experimental or theoretical data from the literature. Through computational modelling, one can efficiently screen materials for specific physicochemical properties and create a high-quality database of descriptors with multiple applications.

Intrinsic descriptors of NMs, i.e., physicochemical properties of the NM alone and which are independent of whether the NM is in dispersion or not, are important inputs to computational model examining the behaviour of NMs in environments such as human cells and their biological activity or adverse effects, and in predicting molecular initiating events (MIEs) leading to certain (known) Adverse Outcomes Pathways (AOP). NMs exhibit geometric structures with diverse shapes or forms and sizes. These characteristics, and in particular the size, may alter the properties of NMs drastically as a result of the so-called quantum confinement effects and as a result of the influence of surface properties exceeding those of core material properties. Thus, we divide descriptors into (1) size-dependent ones and (2) size-independent ones. Moreover, very large NMs (1D, 2D, or 3D) of any shape (sphere, cylinder, rod, etc.) exhibit an electronic band structure that is characteristic of continuous solids. Therefore, we approximate NMs with a radius exceeding 50 nm as continuous solids using 3D periodic boundary conditions.

For the **quantum mechanical modelling of materials**, i.e., the calculation of **electronic structure properties**, we employ *ab initio*, Density Functional Theory (DFT) and semi-empirical methods. *Ab initio* methods, such as Hartree-Fock (HF), Møller–Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) and coupled-cluster (CC)

approaches are limited to generally small NM sizes. Local approaches of the MP2 and CC methods are applicable to larger systems but are still restricted to the few-hundred-atom sizes (corresponding to NMs up to about 1 nm in diameter). Moderate size NMs with up to a few thousand atoms (approaching 10 nm diameter depending on the material composition) can be described by DFT methods. Thus, while DFT is in principle applicable to realistic NMs, depending on the material system and methodology (periodic boundary conditions, basis sets, self-consistent field (SCF) convergence implementations, optimization method), for screening purposes a few orders of magnitudes speed-up, by semi-empirical methods, is needed. Thus, we perform most quantum chemical calculations at the semi-empirical level, applicable to systems up to 5000 atoms (up to 2 nm radius in the case of nanoparticles (NPs) containing metal atoms and 10 nm radius for CNTs) and cross-validate the results with more accurate methods (*ab initio* or DFT) and, if available, with literature data (mainly experimental) or analytical relations. For intrinsic properties, analytical expressions are commonly defined in a size-independent manner [8] and are therefore limited in their use.

For the **classical molecular modelling** of NMs, aiming to obtain structural and thermodynamic properties of NPs, we have carried out both molecular dynamics and molecular mechanics simulations employing classical force fields. Although the level of resolution is coarser than those of quantum mechanical methods, classical methods are readily applicable to larger NMs; e.g., we could compute properties of a crystal NM with the radii of up to 100 nm, which corresponds to 10 million atoms. For amorphous NMs, we have been able to quantify the variation of the materials' properties during their cooling starting from elevated temperatures above the melting point to lower than room temperature. Classical methods can be used for exploring large sets of NMs with varying chemical composition and structures and for identification of the most promising NMs which can be further studied in more detail using the much computationally expensive quantum methods.

We have demonstrated that NM structures can be represented by [7]:

- 1) bulk structures that are most likely associated with the core of an NM and its core properties; and
- 2) surface structures that are associated with the surface of an NM and its surface properties.

Electronic structure properties, such as bandgaps and ionisation potentials need to be determined using accurate calculation methods so that a comparison between different materials and sizes of NMs is meaningful. Although *ab initio* methods such as CC are the most accurate way to evaluate the electronic structure, their application is limited by the system size. Therefore, we only use *ab initio* methods for cross-validation with DFT methods and, eventually, with semi-empirical methods, i.e., to semi-empirical parameterizations based on the HF or the DFTB formalism and focus on descriptors that are linearly size-dependent or independent of the NM size, limiting the calculations to systems with a relatively small number of atoms (<5000 atoms as noted above). Here, we used the following semi-empirical codes: MOPAC [9] in its PM6-D3 parametrization [10] where the one and two-electron integrals are parametrized for all atoms of a molecular system in a pairwise interaction manner, and the GFN-xTB code [11-14] in its GFN0-xTB, GFN1-xTB and GFN2-xTB parameterizations. The MOPAC code [9] was used for several descriptors, while the GFN-xTB code [11-14], known to be an efficient computational tool regarding speed, for other properties related to biological activity including nanotoxicity or cytotoxicity. Furthermore, with its generic force field (GFN-FF) [15] we performed MD simulations to optimise the NM structures and calculate descriptors related to the atomic structure of the NM, such as vibrational frequencies.

Additional structural and thermodynamic properties were determined using reliable empirical force fields. For metallic NMs, we have found that force fields based on the embedded atom model provide an accurate description of the bulk properties and are transferable to systems of NMs contained in vacuum. For metal oxide NMs, we adopted the rigid-ion description of the Born model which is suitable for ionic solids. In this model, the energy between two ions is calculated by partitioning the energy into long-range Coulombic interactions and short-range interactions that approximate Pauli repulsions and van der Waals attractions between ions. The short-range term is modelled by the Buckingham potential. All classical calculations have been carried out using the LAMMPS code [16], which is a portable and parallelized code with numerous built-in potential expressions for material science applications. The interface with OpenKIM [17] eliminates the

need to manually specify the potential parameters which can, in some cases, be automatically retrieved from the OpenKIM library.

We give a brief review of the two quantum mechanical semi-empirical codes, MOPAC & GFN-xTB, that we have primarily used in the calculation of intrinsic descriptors of NMs (electronic properties) with a rather detailed description of the calculation setups with both codes of some advanced intrinsic descriptors of NMs such as bandgaps, ionisation potentials, orbital energies (HOMO and LUMO), electron affinities, electronegativities, atomic charges, dipole moments, static polarizabilities, dispersion energies and/or Hamaker constants, Fukui and global electrophilicity indexes, and absolute hardnesses. All **electronic structure descriptors** mentioned here refer to the properties of the electronic ground state of an NM. It is also worth noting that, although we acknowledge that relativistic effects for heavy elements, e.g., Ag and Au metals, exist, we have included them in an implicit manner only. Similarly, we did not consider bond-breaking electron correlation effects and multireference wave functions. Only the lowest spin state is considered in a single determinant total wave function ansatz, and only in the case of the NM descriptors or surfaces obtained with the SIESTA code [18] we perform spin-polarised calculations. In future work, we would like to scan different spin states of NMs and point out the most stable ground state structure by acknowledging the existing literature, and perhaps in this context to relate also with the term “magic numbers” that have been introduced for a few systems for the most stable ground state structures of metal and metal oxides clusters. Furthermore, a more systematic search for each compound of interest could be performed, by increasing the number of atoms by one unit only in each new calculation, to incorporate the full dependence of a descriptor on the size of a particular material, and to determine if there are points of departure from linear relationships as the NM size increases. For all **electronic structure descriptors**, we approximate NMs with large diameters above 100 nm by bulk systems with 3D periodic boundary conditions, while we explicitly model sizes up to 2 and 10 nm for metal(-oxides) and CNTs, respectively.

Similarly, we highlight the relevant features of the employed classical molecular dynamics / mechanics code, LAMMPS, and proceed with a concise description of the simulation protocol for the preparation of the crystal and amorphous NMs as well as for the calculation of the desired descriptors of NMs such as the number of metal/oxygen atoms in the core and the shell regions of the NM, the average potential energy of all/metal/oxygen atoms in NM, the lattice energy of the whole NM as well as the average coordination number for any group of atoms. Although certain polarizability effects are present in the metal oxide NMs, we have neglected them when adopting the rigid ion Born model; we have attempted to include these effects implicitly via suitably adjusting the parameters of the Born model. In future work, we would like to extend our approach by adopting core-shell and Drude polarizable force fields whenever they are available for the NMs of interest. We acknowledge that it would increase the complexity of the model two-fold with all of the related implications in required memory and computational power requirements, but it would lead to an explicit description of polarisation while keeping the classical framework.

2. Methodology

2.1. Modelling of nanostructures

The modelling of the **electronic properties** of NMs is performed as follows:

- 1) Bulk structures are modelled by constructing crystal or amorphous supercells. The DFT method (SIESTA, [18]) is used to optimise the periodic or amorphous solid structures with the PBE functional [19] and a DZP basis set, which is a set of atom-centred (localised) Wannier wave functions. Troullier-Martins pseudopotentials [20] are applied to substitute the core electrons and Monkhorst-Pack meshes [21] are used for sampling the Brillouin zone.
- 2) Surface structures are presented as crystal or amorphous xy -periodic slabs with a vacuum above and below the surface slab in the z -direction in a supercell and/or as molecular surface clusters. Similarly, the DFT method (SIESTA, [18]) is used to optimise the periodic or amorphous solid structures with the PBE functional [19] and a DZP basis set. Troullier-Martins pseudopotentials [20] are applied to substitute the core electrons and Monkhorst-Pack meshes [21] are used for the point sampling of the Brillouin zone integration.
- 3) Several cases of specific geometries are modelled: Wulff or spherical NM structures (see Figure 1), carbon nanotubes and graphene sheets and other shapes of NMs (rods, cylinder, etc.).

In the bulk and surface calculations the supercells are constructed from the input of the crystallographic geometry, i.e., cartesian coordinates and lattice parameters of a unit cell of a material, given in a crystallographic information file (CIF); the information is commonly obtained by DFT calculations or X-ray diffraction measurements and the files are available to download from open databases, such as Materials Project <https://materialsproject.org/> [22] or COD <http://www.crystallography.net/cod/> [23-25] for a particular phase of an NM classified by the group symmetry of the solid. The surface structures, i.e., surface slabs, are obtained by cutting the surface of the bulk structure unit cell in a specific orientation which is characterised by the three Miller indices for each direction and replicating this to a specific size of the surface slab. Typically, several sets of Miller indices were considered since it is known that physicochemical properties vary between different phases of a material and Miller indices of the surface slabs. Stoichiometric Wulff or spherical NM structures of metal and metal oxide materials are constructed using crystallographic web tools -<https://nanocrystal.vi-seem.eu/> [26] or <http://crystalium.materialsvirtuallab.org/> [27-29], using the knowledge of the surface energies of low index surfaces of the specific materials (see Figure 1). The crystallographic webtool <https://nanocrystal.vi-seem.eu/> [26] is used for the modelling of spherical metal or metal oxide NPs. In a similar manner, organic material structures such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene and graphite sheets are obtained from visualisation tools such as Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD) <http://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Research/vmd/> [30], and Avogadro <http://avogadro.cc/> [31]. In Avogadro [31], one can replicate to a specific size from the unit cell of the specific material (crystal).

For larger spherical NPs, in-house python scripts are used that replicate the crystal structure of the selected metal oxide or pure metal crystal structure in all three directions, and afterwards, a spherical particle is cut out. As the last step, some atoms with a given charge are removed from the surface of the NP to ensure electroneutrality of the NP. Molecular Dynamics together with Buckingham potential and Coulombic force field parameters are used to optimise and calculate different parameters for the generated structure. For finding optimal core radius and calculation of coordination numbers for different regions a web-based tool has been developed (<https://nanogen.me>). As a first step, the centre-of-mass for the input NP is calculated and from there the radius of the NP is evaluated. Next, the coordination number for each atom is calculated using the kNN algorithm in conjunction with the estimated bond length between atoms. An optimizer uses the calculated coordination numbers to define the best core radius for a given NM. The best core radius is defined as the radius where the highest change in an average value for shell atom coordination numbers occurs, while there should not be much change for the average value for core atom coordination numbers.

Figure 1: For the calculation of quantum intrinsic descriptors, Wulff (left) and spherical shape (right) NMs are modelled with the crystallographic web tool [26] and, in the case of the Wulff NMs with the aid of the Crystallium materials virtual lab [27-29] to provide data on the surface energies. The images show an example of an Au NP of 2 nm radius for both structure types.

For amorphous NMs, we have built upon and extended the previous computational procedure. In particular, an initial bulk configuration (periodic supercell) is constructed by multiplying the crystal unit cell of the NM of interest eight times in each cartesian coordinate. The supercell is thermalized at 300 K under constant volume and temperature for 1 ns using the Langevin thermostat. Subsequently, the supercell is heated to above the melting point (for instance 1400 K for Au & 2100 K for Pt) using a constant heating rate of 10 K/ns with a simulation under constant pressure and temperature. The temperature and the pressure have been controlled using a Langevin thermostat and a Nose-Hoover barostat [32] with a coupling time of 0.1 ps and 1.0 ps, respectively. The equations of motion are integrated using the velocity-Verlet algorithm with a time step of 1 fs. When the final temperature is reached, a further constant pressure & temperature simulation of 20 ns with the same settings but without heating is carried out. The final amorphous configuration is replicated sufficiently many times in all three cartesian coordinates to form an NP. Currently, our implementation supports the creation of either a spherical or a cubic NM. The desired radius of a sphere or cube length is determined by the user. A short simulation under constant temperature, where the NM is placed in vacuum, is carried out for 5 ns to allow primarily the relaxation of the NM surface. The created NM is cooled down to 100 K following the stepwise procedure of Martin et al [33]: at each step, the temperature is instantaneously decreased by 100 K and a further simulation under constant temperature is performed for 20 ns using the same settings as previously. All simulations have been performed using the LAMMPS software. A representative visualisation of an amorphous SiO₂ NP of 5 nm diameter at 300 K which has been created using the above procedure is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: A simulation snapshot of an amorphous SiO₂ NM of 5 nm diameter at 300 K.

The procedure to generate amorphous NMs has been implemented in a python script. LAMMPS is invoked as a dynamic library. The force field parameters are retrieved automatically from the OpenKIM Repository (<https://openkim.org/>). The MD simulations are performed in parallel using the MPI library. The initial crystal structure is converted from the CIF file format to LAMMPS compatible input files using the cif2cell tool [34]. A schematic of the workflow is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic of the implemented procedure to generate amorphous NM structures.

While automating the computational workflow for the prediction of the nanodescriptors for both crystal and amorphous NMs, we identified several missing force fields, especially for metal oxides in the

OpenKIM library. Thus, in the context of the NanoSolveIT, we contributed the parameters for the following systems into this open library:

- Cr - LAMMPS angular-dependent potential developed by Howells and Mishin (2018) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_ADH_P_HowellsMishin_2018_Cr__SM_884076133432_000) [35]
- CeO₂ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential developed by Arima *et al.*, (2005) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_ArimaYamasakiTorikai_2005_CeO__SM_328512278696_000) [36]
- SiO₂ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for SiO₂ developed by Carré *et al.*, (2008) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_CarreHorbachIspas_2008_SiO__SM_886641404623_000) [37]
- La₂O₃ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for La₂O₃ developed by Fang *et al.*, (2014) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_FangKeltyHe_2014_LaO__SM_576027677976_000) [38]
- NiO - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for NiO developed by Fisher and Matsubara (2005) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_FisherMatsubara_2005_NiO__SM_337243826931_000) [39]
- MnO₂ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for MnO₂ developed by Sayle *et al.*, (2005) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_SayleCatlowMaphanga_2005_MnO__SM_757974494010_000) [40]
- Al₂O₃ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for α -Al₂O₃ developed by Sun *et al.*, (2006) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_SunStirnerHagston_2006_AlO__SM_466046725502_000) [41]
- MgO - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for MgO developed by Sun *et al.*, (2006) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_SunStirnerHagston_2006_MgO__SM_152356670345_000) [41]
- Fe₂O₃ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for α -Fe₂O₃ (hematite) reported by Vaari (2015) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_Vaari_2015_FeO__SM_672759489721_000) [42]
- Cr₂O₃ - LAMMPS Buckingham potential for Cr₂O₃ reported by Wang, Shin and Shin (2019) (Extended KIM ID: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_WangShinShin_2019_CrO__SM_295921111679_000) [43]

2.2. Methodology for calculation of intrinsic descriptors of NMs

The methodology for the calculation of intrinsic descriptors of NMs such as quantum mechanical properties is reported in [7], and, for molecular properties, it is described in [3]. The software for the effective theoretical calculation of the molecular and electronic properties of NMs has been chosen after careful testing of the various properties with respect to the method and computational tool that performs most efficiently, i.e., in terms of properties implemented in open source codes (free licensed software), however, the important factor for the final decision is the balance between accuracy and cost of the calculation setup [3,7].

The two semi-empirical QM codes and one classical MD code most widely used in NanoSolveIT are briefly described here:

1. MOPAC

MOPAC is a computer program [9], which is widely used in the calculation of the geometries and energies of biological systems (proteins), crystals, co-crystals, polymers and other condensed phase systems. MOPAC 2016 [9] has been improved with regards to the description of intermolecular interaction by incorporating London dispersion forces and Hydrogen bonding corrections. Also, fast property prediction algorithms for screening libraries of drug-sized molecules for a wide range of properties including pKa are implemented [44]. Thus, the generation of electronic descriptors for QSARs is the canonical route. The effect of solvents can be captured by the COSMO method [45-46] where both ground and excited state geometries of solvated systems are optimised. It is straightforward to produce the intrinsic properties of interest: band gaps, HOMO and LUMO orbital states, electronegativities and absolute hardnesses with good accuracy and moderate computational cost.

2. GFN-xTB

The extended Tight-Binding (xTB) software covers mostly quantum chemistry based semi-empirical methods for the fast and reasonably accurate description of large molecules in gas and condensed phase [11-14]. Furthermore, GFN-FF, a completely automated partially polarizable generic force-field for the accurate description of structures and dynamics of large molecules across the periodic table has been implemented.

This method combines FF speed with almost QM accuracy [11-14]. The main focus of GFN-FF [15] is directed towards the description of bio-macromolecular systems such as metalloproteins, supramolecular assemblies and metal-organic frameworks. It is intended for use as a versatile tool for drug design in life sciences and structure screening in various fields of chemistry [11-14]. GFN-FF [15] introduces an approximation to the remaining quantum mechanics in GFNO-xTB by replacing the extended Hückel theory with molecular mechanical bond stretch, bond angle and torsion angle terms for the description of covalent bonds. To remain accurate in the description of conjugated systems, GFN-FF retains an iterative Hückel scheme for a selected set of atoms. The resulting bond orders obtained by a Hückel calculation influence the force constants and energy-relevant parameters of the system [11-14]. The FF parameters are fitted to reproduce B97-3c minimum geometries and frequencies [47]. This code is primarily used to produce dipole moments, polarizabilities, ionisation potentials, electron affinities and the global electrophilicity index with good accuracy running efficiently on high-performance computers. xTB is fully open source under the L-GPL3 licence (<https://github.com/grimme-lab/xtb>) with up-to-date documentation (<https://xtb-docs.readthedocs.io>). Small code modifications have been adapted specifically for the needs of NanoSolveIT.

3. LAMMPS

The LAMMPS software package [16] is a classical molecular dynamics code. It can simulate polymeric, biological, solid-state (metals, ceramics, oxides), coarse-grained or macroscopic systems using a variety of interatomic potentials (force fields) and boundary conditions. It can model systems with millions or billions of particles. LAMMPS can be built as a library and be invoked by a Python wrapper, making possible the implementation of automated computational workflows. It has access to the OpenKIM Repository, a curated repository of tested interatomic potentials which are verified for coding integrity as well as material property predictions. The effect of solvents can be captured either explicitly, by including solvent molecules in the simulation box, or implicitly, by implicit solvent potentials, such as the Debye model, coupled to Langevin dynamics. LAMMPS can produce descriptors related to the size of the NM (such as its surface area and volume), the chemical composition (such as total number of atoms, number of atoms in the core & shell regions, number of oxygens in each region), the potential energy (such as the average potential energy per atom in each region and the lattice energy), the topology of the NM structure (such as the average coordination number of each chemical species in the core and the shell region) as well as the interacting forces (such as the tangent and parallel force exerted on each atom belonging to either the core or the shell region).

In the following, we introduce each of the intrinsic descriptors with an emphasis on the definition but also its meaning for bionano interactions and a discussion whether a relationship between the descriptor and a particular biological activity can be established. The method which is used to evaluate the descriptor is given as well. It is worth noting that an optimization of the geometric structures is not an essential step for the calculation of intrinsic NM descriptors, in particular for monomeric NMs for which only a self-consistent field (SCF) calculation (MOPAC) or self-consistent charge (SCC) calculation (GFN-xTB) is necessary. However, in the case of the periodic bulk calculations for solids, we have optimised the geometric structures with DFT using the SIESTA code [18] and the PBE functional [19] to ensure that the calculated supercell structures of the NMIs under investigation are in good agreement with experimental and/or other theoretical approaches, as follows:

a) Band gap by PM6-D3 (MOPAC) or PBE (SIESTA)

The bandgap is derived from the knowledge of single-particle energy levels (see b) and c)), where the difference between the two energy levels, HOMO and LUMO, is equal to the value of the band gap. Similarly, the difference between the valence band maximum (VBM) and conduction band minimum (CBM) energy is considered as the bandgap in solids (bulk calculations with SIESTA [18]). The information about the energy levels is derived from the calculation of eigenvalues of the effective Hamiltonian, and used to plot the density of states (DOS), i.e., the density of electron states at each energy, for the entire set of states that form the electron bands of a solid system. DOS can be obtained with a utility/tool within the SIESTA code [18] and in the case of bulk calculations with MOPAC the same script can be used. The knowledge of the VBM energy

level in solids and the HOMO energy level of an NM (MOPAC calculations) are important energy levels impacting electron transfer from the NM to a biomolecule, for instance to an unoccupied orbital of a protein. Similarly, an electron transfer from the biomolecule to the conduction band or the LUMO of a material may initiate a reaction between the biomolecule and the material or a transfer of an electron from the conduction band or the LUMO of a material to the biomolecule, after the excitation of an electron from the VBM or the HOMO to the CBM or the LUMO, are important energy levels to compare with the biological redox potential of a biomolecule, to draw conclusions as to whether electron transfer reactions can occur or not between the NM and the specific biomolecule.

b) HOMO by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)

The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energy of a NM or the valence band energy level of a NM is the highest energy of an electron in an orbital (bound) state that impacts the bonding with other molecules or electron transfer reactions. Its energy can be compared to the biological redox potential of a biomolecule to make inferences as to whether electron transfer reactions can occur or not between the NM and the biomolecule (e.g., a protein) via a direct electron transfer.

c) LUMO by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)

The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energy of a NM or the conduction band energy of a NM is the lowest energy of an electron in an orbital state of the continuum. The process is as follows: After the excitation of an electron from the valence band to the conduction band of the NM the electron transfer reaction occurs to an unoccupied electron state of the biomolecule and a bionano interaction is initiated.

d) Mulliken electronegativity and absolute hardness by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)

The Mulliken electronegativity and the Parr and Pople absolute hardness are calculated in MOPAC [9] from LUMO and HOMO energies. Mulliken electronegativity is defined as $-\alpha$, where α is the average of the HOMO and LUMO energies, i.e., $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{\text{homo}} + \epsilon_{\text{lumo}})$, and the Parr & Pople absolute hardness is $\frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{\text{homo}} - \epsilon_{\text{lumo}})$. The electronegativity of a molecular system, as in atoms, is the tendency to attract an electron to itself and can be used to make assumptions about electron transfer reactions with adsorbates on the NM surface, for instance, if the electronegativity of adsorbate is larger than that of an NM, then electron transfer occurs from the adsorbate to the NM. An absolute hardness value can be used to characterise the NM in terms of its reactivity with soft materials such as membranes.

e) Intramolecular dispersion energy by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)

The dispersion energy is given by the D3 Grimme correction term [48]. The D3 term provides the dispersion energy contribution in a PM6 calculation and is the sum over pairwise atom-atom contributions.

f) Dipole moment and static polarizability by PM6-D3 (MOPAC) or GFN2-xTB (GFN-xTB)

MOPAC [9] uses the IUPAC chemistry convention to define the direction of the dipole, as being from the negative to the positive centre, see: <http://goldbook.iupac.org/html/E/E01929.html>. This is the opposite of the physics convention. For neutral systems, the dipole moment is calculated from the atomic charges and the lone-pairs. The keyword STATIC is set in the input for the calculation of static polarizabilities that enables the finite-field method using both an energy and a dipole moment expansion. An electric field gradient is applied to the system, and the response is calculated. The dipole and polarizability are calculated in two different ways, from the change in the heat of formation and the change in the dipole moment. An estimation of the imprecision of the calculation can be obtained by comparing the two quantities. We gather the data of the dipole moments and polarizabilities that result from a converged dipole calculation.

g) Ionisation potential or electron affinity by GFN1-xTB or GFN2-xTB (ΔSCF , GFN-xTB)

Descriptors, such as vertical ionisation potentials and electron affinities describe how easily an electron can be removed from an NM or can be added to it. The ionisation potential (energy) or electron affinity is the difference in total energy for the cationic or anionic system and the neutral system, where an electron is removed from or attached to the ground state of the neutral system. The energies are computed by a ΔSCF or more precisely a ΔSCC calculation in the tight-binding formalism. In such a set up the relaxation of the orbital states is considered in contrast to the Koopmans theorem approximation, while the relaxation of the atomic structures as well as relativistic corrections or electron correlation effects are neglected during the ionisation or attachment process. This approach provides increased accuracy with no additional cost of the

calculation, in comparison to the Koopmans level ionisation potentials, where the canonical orbitals in the HF formalism are used to describe ionisation potentials. Furthermore, we focus on closed-shell structures of NMs, i.e., on structures with an even number of electrons, to be able to compare ionisation potentials and electron affinities across the materials of interest.

h) Global electrophilicity index by GFN1-xTB or GFN2-xTB (ΔSCF , GFN-xTB)

The global electrophilic index and Fukui index are indices that represent the nucleophilicity (susceptibility) to electrophilic attack of an atom. The higher the Fukui index of an atom the higher the electrophilicity. Similar conclusions can be made from the global electrophilic index of a molecular system.

i) Atomic charges by GFN2-xTB (GFN-xTB)

Atomic charges are written out for each atom in atomic units (a.u). They can be negative or positive.

j) Descriptors related to chemical composition: logarithm with base 10 of

- the total number of atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the NM
- the number of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region
- the number of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region.

k) Descriptors related to the size of the NM:

- The diameter of the NM in Ångstrom
- The surface area of the NM in squared Ångstrom
- The volume of the NM in cubic Ångstrom.

l) Descriptors related to the potential energy:

- the average potential energy of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the NMP in eV
- the average potential energy of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region in eV
- the average potential energy of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region in eV.

m) Descriptors related to the lattice energy:

- Lattice energy of NM in eV
- Lattice energy of bulk material - Lattice energy of NM in eV
- Lattice energy of NP divided by the NM diameter in eV/Å
- Lattice energy of NP divided by the NM surface area in eV/Å²
- Lattice energy of NP divided by the NM volume in eV/Å³

n) Descriptors related to the topology:

- the average coordination parameter of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the NM
- the average coordination parameter of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region
- the average coordination parameter of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region.

o) Descriptors related to force:

- the average norm of force of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in eV/Å
- the average norm of force of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region in eV/Å
- the average norm of force of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region in eV/Å
- the average norm of the force projection normal to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in eV/Å
- the average norm of the force projection normal to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region in eV/Å
- the average norm of the force projection normal to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region in eV/Å
- the average norm of the force projection parallel to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in eV/Å

- the average norm of the force projection parallel to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the surface region in eV/Å
- the average norm of the force projection parallel to NM surface of all atoms / metal atoms / oxygen atoms in the core region in eV/Å

2.3. Representative example input and output of GFN-xTB

As input values, only the GFN-xTB cartesian coordinates and the elemental composition are required, from which fully automatically all potential energy terms related to the NM are constructed. An output example of the calculation of the ionisation potential of an anatase TiO₂ Wulff structure of 2nm radius with the GFN1-xTB method generated by the following program call “xtb coord --vomega --iterations 3000” is given in Figure 4. The setup of such a calculation is as follows:

```

.....
:                               SETUP                               :
.....
: # basis functions              14820                            :
: # atomic orbitals              14079                            :
: # shells                       6669                            :
: # electrons                    11856                            :
: # halogen bonds                 0                               :
: max. iterations                 3000                            :
: Hamiltonian                    GFN1-xTB                        :
: restarted?                      false                          :
: GBSA solvation                  false                          :
: PC potential                    false                          :
: electronic temp.                300.0000000 K                  :
: accuracy                        1.0000000                    :
: -> integral cutoff              0.2500000E+02                  :
: -> integral neglect              0.1000000E-07                  :
: -> SCF convergence              0.1000000E-05 Eh                :
: -> wf. convergence              0.2000000E-04 e                :
: Broyden damping                 0.4000000                    :
.....

```

The descriptor calculations were run on the UCD computational GPU server using an efficient implementation of the code with a shared memory OpenMP parallelisation, to calculate larger systems and an appropriate OpenMP stack size with a reasonable distribution of the number of threads in the OpenMP section. The default linear algebra backend of xTB is the Math Kernel Library, which usually comes as an OpenMP threaded version and respects the settings of the OpenMP parallelisation.

```

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
kktotsi@bionanogpu: ~/XTB/atanase_Wulff/znm/vomega
-----
| vertical delta SCC IP calculation |
-----
:
: SETUP
:
: # basis functions      14820
: # atomic orbitals     14079
: # shells               6669
: # electrons           11855
: # halogen bonds       0
: max. iterations       3000
: Hamiltonian           GFN1-xTB
: restarted?            true
: GBSA solvation        false
: PC potential          false
: electronic temp.     300.000000 K
: accuracy              1.0000000
: -> Integral cutoff    0.2500000E+02
: -> Integral neglect   0.1000000E-07
: -> SCF convergence    0.1000000E-05 Eh
: -> wf convergence     0.2000000E-04 e
: Broyden damping       0.4000000
:
-----
Iter  E          dE          RMSdg      gap      omega  full diag
-----
1 -7911.1804499 -0.791110E+04  0.101E-02  0.00  0.0 T
2 -7910.1742292  0.926221E+00  0.290E-01  0.00  1.0 T
3 -7910.8676002 -0.693371E+00  0.148E-01  0.00  1.0 T
4 -7910.2020622  0.665538E+00  0.249E-01  0.00  1.0 T
5 -7909.6422661  0.559796E+00  0.279E-01  0.00  1.0 T
6 -7910.8284334 -0.118617E+01  0.139E-01  0.00  1.0 T
7 -7911.0193698 -0.190934E+00  0.844E-02  0.00  1.0 T
8 -7911.0318180 -0.124482E-01  0.771E-02  0.00  1.0 T
9 -7911.0129476  0.188704E-01  0.821E-02  0.00  1.0 T
10 -7911.0231494 -0.452017E-01  0.669E-02  0.00  1.0 T
11 -7911.0666389 -0.848953E-02  0.608E-02  0.00  1.0 T
12 -7910.9817037  0.849352E-01  0.969E-02  0.00  1.0 T
13 -7910.6895912  0.292112E+00  0.161E-01  0.00  1.0 T
14 -7910.9690153 -0.276424E+00  0.101E-01  0.00  1.0 T
15 -7911.0129218 -0.469065E-01  0.879E-02  0.00  1.0 T
16 -7910.9789519  0.339699E-01  0.100E-01  0.00  1.0 T
17 -7910.9131994  0.657525E-01  0.118E-01  0.00  1.0 T
18 -7910.9690927 -0.558933E-01  0.109E-01  0.00  1.0 T
19 -7910.9350972  0.348055E-01  0.111E-01  0.00  1.0 T
20 -7910.9978671 -0.627799E-01  0.841E-02  0.00  1.0 T
21 -7911.0233704 -0.255033E-01  0.796E-02  0.00  1.0 T
22 -7911.0428265 -0.194560E-01  0.662E-02  0.00  1.0 T
23 -7911.0441308 -0.138357E-02  0.694E-02  0.00  1.0 T
24 -7911.0409440 -0.571395E-02  0.646E-02  0.00  1.0 T
25 -7911.0659908 -0.161469E-01  0.535E-02  0.00  1.0 T
-----
1102,9 13%

```

```

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
kktotsi@bionanogpu: ~/XTB/atanase_Wulff/znm/vomega
61 -7911.1025215 -0.164272E-06  0.968E-05  0.00  21.9 T
*** convergence criteria satisfied after 61 iterations ***
-----
# Occupation      Energy/Eh      Energy/eV
-----
1 2.0000          -1.5586306     -42.4127
...
5922 1.1391        -0.5987176     -16.2919
5923 1.1099        -0.5986611     -16.2904
5924 1.1081        -0.5986577     -16.2903
5925 1.0801        -0.5986040     -16.2888
5926 1.0707        -0.5985800     -16.2884
5927 1.0682        -0.5985812     -16.2882
5928 1.0610        -0.5985674     -16.2878 (HOMO)
5929 1.0091        -0.5984686     -16.2852 (LUMO)
5930 1.0844        -0.5984596     -16.2849
5931 0.9853        -0.5984234     -16.2839
5932 0.9815        -0.5984161     -16.2837
5933 0.9505        -0.5983572     -16.2821
...
14079          904.0174699     24599.5075
-----
HL-Gap          0.0000988 Eh    0.0027 eV
Fermi-level     -0.5984513 Eh   -16.2847 eV
-----
SCC (total)     0 d, 11 h, 44 min, 38.035 sec
SCC setup      ... 0 min, 2.202 sec ( 0.005%)
Dispersion     ... 0 min, 1.579 sec ( 0.004%)
Classical contributions ... 0 min, 0.544 sec ( 0.003%)
Integral evaluation ... 30 min, 11.831 sec ( 4.286%)
Iterations     ... 667 min, 10.533 sec ( 94.684%)
molecular gradient ... 6 min, 38.249 sec ( 0.942%)
printout      ... 0 min, 33.097 sec ( 0.078%)
-----
SUMMARY
-----
:: total energy      -7909.554907782087 Eh ::
:: gradient norm    1.243532189456 Eh/a0 ::
:: HOMO-LUMO gap    0.002687517556 eV ::
-----
:: SCC energy      -7911.102521544160 Eh ::
:: -> electrostatic 70.970023474457 Eh ::
:: repulsion energy 10.871441293583 Eh ::
:: dispersion energy -9.323827523111 Eh ::
:: halogen bond corr. 0.000000000000 Eh ::
:: add. restraining 0.000000000000 Eh ::
:: total charge    1.000131389134 e ::
-----
empirical IP shift (eV): 4.8455
delta SCC IP (eV): 11.0844
-----
1148,8 14%

```

Figure 4: Snapshots of the output of a GFN1-xTB ionisation potential calculation of an anatase TiO₂ Wulff NM structure with a 2 nm radius.

2.4. MODA templates

2.4.1. MODA (Model Oriented Data Analysis)

MODA templates are model oriented data analysis tools in the form of text documents or spreadsheets, which have been developed by the materials modelling community with an ultimate goal to develop a unified language for description and documentation of material models, computational workflows and computed properties, to facilitate their utilisation in material design and in regulation. Classification of materials can be done using the ID and the core chemistry of the material. Providing completed MODA templates for all NanoSolveIT models has been agreed upon in the consortium, and is considered as a requirement to accommodate the needs of its users and to expand their usability, by automatisation or standardisation, for example, by using drop-down lists (an EMMC application is available for registered users) to avoid multiple variants of the same concept.

OSMO is an ontology for simulation, modelling, and optimisation, introduced on the basis of MODA, a previously developed semi-intuitive graph notation for workflows in materials modelling [49]. The OSMO ontology [49] enhances the original MODA by being machine-processable, amenable to automated reasoning by semantic technology, and by which workflow semantics in materials modelling are captured in a way that is closely aligned and interoperable with the whole family of semantic assets presently under development in the context of several infrastructures and projects. By providing a common semantic basis for workflows that were designed with different tools, OSMO can be employed to consistently integrate data provenance descriptions for materials modelling data from diverse sources. The detailed description of the four types of section entities (use cases, models, solvers, and processors) in OSMO follows the specification from MODA closely. Particle-based methods are defined to be atomistic if the particles represent single atoms and mesoscopic if they represent multiple atoms; by this categorization, e.g., molecular models following the united-atom approach are regarded as mesoscopic.

2.4.2. Templates

For the templates we used the EMMC as the source: <https://emmc.info/moda-workflow-templates/>.

The completed MODA templates for the NanoSolveIT QM and MD descriptors are given in Appendix I. For instance, the MODA template under the title “MODA for calculation of full-particle nanodescriptors simulated in the NanoSolveIT project” has been created for the descriptors of groups (j)-(o) from section 3.2 above.

3. Conclusions

We have compiled a list of computable intrinsic NM properties relevant for NM safety assessment. It is known from previous studies that wide band gaps, high ionisation potentials and low electronegativities or electrophilicities, which are characteristic for low reactivity, are associated with safer NMs. Still, one has to find the balance between the search for optimal materials for certain applications and requirements that they are safe, and rank descriptors with their importance for safety and applicability as well as their functionality for the desired application. All the methodologies described in this report to compute the intrinsic properties of NMs are designed to provide data in a fast and accurate manner with the ultimate goal to serve as input data for further computational analysis, using machine learning techniques, to evaluate how safe the materials are within the general scope of the project and its IATA. From the core materials alone, we can establish valuable relationships between intrinsic properties and the biological activity of the NMs. Available literature data of measurements of intrinsic properties of NMs serve the analysis very well and we always compare our computed NMs properties with data that is already available.

In practice, one can deal with very large sizes of NMs and their aggregates or biomolecule-coated NMs. In laboratory conditions, smaller NMs of various compositions can be synthesised depending on the purpose of research, and, in particular, modelled, to study many chemical properties, e.g., the catalytic activity of NMs where quantum mechanical modelling has been found very successful. As mentioned above,

the calculations of the **electronic structure descriptors** are limited by the size of the NP, i.e., it is not yet possible to consider long-range interactions of NMs quantum mechanically. In contrast, our periodic boundary conditions calculations can be used to represent results of large sizes of NMs, above 50 nm radius, where the material is considered as bulk. Additionally, with MD simulations we can study larger sizes of NMs and make conclusions about the size dependence of the descriptors, etc., as shown here.

Notably, different phases of the material may show different physicochemical properties and biological activities. The same applies to surfaces with different Miller indices. The materials and material properties we discuss here are more likely to represent ideal conditions, i.e., experimental lab conditions of pristine materials and material functions that are used in many technological applications. We also have considered so far the materials with hydroxylation on their surfaces, e.g. hydroxylated TiO₂ surfaces or particles with a specific percentage of attached -COOH and -NH₂ groups such as surface-functionalized CNTs and their charged groups. For the latter, the effect of functionalization on the NMs' intrinsic properties is studied. However, a plethora of materials that appear in many technological products, but also in a range of environmental compartments, e.g., the human cell or biological systems within a cell, are much more complex as environmental conditions influence the material structure, surface and material properties. In addition, electronic or molecular and structural properties, as well as dynamical or extrinsic properties, can be modified, as desired, by adding elemental atoms into a material (e.g., chemically doped materials) or by making alloys, which both exist also naturally and are widely used in many technological applications. Structural complexity can also be increased by adding layers viz. coatings to a specific material for various reasons. In this context, computational scanning of the NMs can help design materials that have beneficial properties, combined with a decreased biological activity or reactivity and eventually toxicity. Thus, future studies for generating data for the nanoPharos computational NMs descriptors database may include the study of more complex materials and methods to efficiently manipulate the structure of a material (in terms of modelling) to gain material properties that allow less reactivity in biological or chemical environments, and finally to extend the library of materials by adding other kinds of materials, e.g., polymers (soft matter) or superconductors.

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Appendix

A) Quantum mechanical descriptors MODA templates

- a) *Band gap by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)*
- b) *HOMO by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)*
- c) *LUMO by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)*
- d) *Mulliken electronegativity and absolute hardness by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)*
- e) *Intramolecular dispersion energy by PM6-D3 (MOPAC)*
- f) *Dipole moment and static polarizability by GFN2-xTB*
- g) *Ionisation potential or electron affinity by GFN1-xTB or GFN2-xTB (Δ SCF, GFN-xTB)*
- h) *Global electrophilicity index by GFN1-xTB or GFN2-xTB (Δ SCF, GFN-xTB)*
- i) *Atomic charges by GFN2-xTB (GFN-xTB)*

For a) - e), the following MODA template (EMMC) has been created:

Elements in materials modelling

MODA for Band Gap Calculations

OVERVIEW of the simulation						
1	USER CASE	<i>Calculation of the electronic band gap of a material</i>				
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>MODEL 1</th> <td><i>Material (electronic)</i></td> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>...</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	MODEL 1	<i>Material (electronic)</i>	...	
MODEL 1	<i>Material (electronic)</i>					
...						
3	PUBLICATION ON THE SIMULATION					
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>Software is free for academic use. MOPAC2016 - Stewart, J. J. P. MOPAC2016: Computational Chemistry, Colorado Springs, CO, USA, 2016</i> http://OpenMOPAC.net				
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	The calculation requires a model for the material structure and input parameters (parametrization of the one and two electron integrals) to calculate orbital energies and the electronic band gap				

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED AND HOW IT FORMS A PART OF THE TOTAL USER CASE	<i>The electronic band structure of the specified material</i>
1.2	MATERIAL	<i>user input - any dielectric material</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>a molecular structure of the material in terms of atomic coordinates: finite size (nanoparticle) or continuous phase</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>N/A</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS ONE SIMULATION	

Material model

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION			
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	<i>Quantum mechanics - Semi-empirical</i>	
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	<i>Atoms (nuclei and electrons)</i>	
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE'S	Equations	<i>Time-independent electronic Schrödinger equation, Hartree-Fock equation</i>
		Physical quantities for each equation	<i>Wave function, Hamiltonian, orbital energy</i>
MATERIALS RELATIONS		MR Equations	<i>Orbital wave functions which describe the electrons of the material in space; parametrization of the Hartree-Fock equation</i>
		Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR	<i>PM6 parametrization of the one and two electron integrals</i>
2.4	SIMULATED INPUT		

Quantum Mechanics

SCF

3 SPECIFIC COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING METADATA			
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Fock diagonalization: eigenvalues</i> <i>Numerical method: variational principle, iterative self-consistent field (SCF)</i>	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	MOPAC2016	
3.3	TIME STEP	N/A	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION <i>Refers to how your computational solver represents the material, properties, equation variables,</i>	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	<i>Orbital energies are computed by diagonalization of the Hartree-Fock equation in a self-consistent field (SCF) whereby the one and two electron integrals are given by parameters which are obtained from ab initio calculations of small systems for the same type of material</i>
		BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	
		ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<i>SCF convergence criteria</i>

For f) - i) following MODA template has been created:

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	Calculation of intrinsic quantum descriptors: ionisation potential, electron affinity, electrophilicity index, static polarisability, dipole moment and atomic charges	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	<i>extended Tight-Binding</i>
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	<i>C. Bannwarth, E. Caldeweyher, S. Ehlert, A. Hansen, P. Pracht, J. Seibert, S. Spicher, S. Grimme WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci., 2020, 11, e01493. DOI: 10.1002/wcms.1493</i>	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>Open source code, L-GPL3 licence.</i>	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	<i>Full geometry of the material as input in XYZ format, descriptor as numerical output.</i>	

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>The quantum mechanical descriptors are to be calculated for a given material.</i>
1.2	MATERIAL	<i>All materials with finite band gaps and a number of atoms below 10000.</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>Atomistic geometry, typically given as XYZ coordinates.</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>not applicable</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<i>not applicable</i>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<i>C. Bannwarth, E. Caldeweyher, S. Ehlert, A. Hansen, P. Pracht, J. Seibert, S. Spicher, S. Grimme WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci., 2020, 11, e01493. DOI: 10.1002/wcms.1493</i>

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	<i>Semi-empirical quantum mechanics via an extended tight-binding model.</i>	
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	<i>Electronic structure</i>	
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	<i>Electronic Schroedinger equation in the Born-Oppenheimer approximation</i>
		Physical quantities	<i>Atomic coordinates, number of electrons</i>
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	<i>Coulomb interaction, Newton forces on atom</i>
		Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR	<i>Molecular orbitals constituting the molecular wave function. Element-specific parameters to reproduce DFT quality references.</i>
2.4	SIMULATED INPUT	<i>not applicable</i>	

3		SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Direct Inversion of Iterated Subspace (DIIS) for self-consistent charge solution, Intels Math Kernel Library (MKL) for matrix operations, Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) algorithm for estimates Hessian in geometry optimization, approximate normal coordinate (ANC) representation.</i>	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	<i>xTB</i> https://github.com/grimme-lab/xtb	
3.3	TIME STEP	<i>Not applicable</i>	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	<i>Minimal single-particle basis set is used to represent the molecular wave function, which gives access to all electronic properties. Solver gives occupation of basis functions for specific input geometry.</i>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<i>Molecules are treated as spatially open systems. Number of electrons is fixed.</i>	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<i>Convergence thresholds for SCC iteration, convergence thresholds for geometry optimizations (numerical derivatives, estimated and realised energy difference)</i>	

4		POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<i>Data can be directly gathered from output: Ionisation potential, electron affinity, global electrophilicity index, atomic charges, dipole moment, and static polarizability</i>	
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<i>Not applicable</i>	
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<i>Not applicable</i>	

B) Molecular dynamics descriptors MODA template

MODA for calculation of full-particle nanodescriptors simulated in project NanoSolveIT

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION		
1	User Case	<i>Structural and energetic nanodescriptors of spherical nanoparticles</i>
2	Chain of Models	Model 1 <i>Material (atomistic)</i>
3	Publication Peer-Reviewing the data	<i>K. Tämm, L. Sikk, J. Burk, R. Rallo, S. Pokhrel, L. Mädler, J. J. Scott-Fordsmann, P. Burk, T. Tamm, Parametrization of nanoparticles: development of full-particle nanodescriptors, Nanoscale, 36, 2016, 16243-16250 J. Burk, L. Sikk, P. Burk, B. B. Manshian, S. J. Soenen, J. J. Scott-Fordsmann, T. Tamm, K. Tämm, Fe-Doped ZnO nanoparticle toxicity: assessment by a new generation of nanodescriptors, Nanoscale, 46, 2018, 21985-21993</i>
4	Access conditions	<i>The software is released under the GNU General Public License (GPL). LAMMPS - Plimpton, P. "Fast Parallel Algorithms for Short-Range Molecular Dynamics", Journal of Computational Physics Volume 117, Issue 1, 1 March 1995, Pages 1-19 https://lammps.sandia.gov/</i>
5	Workflow and its rationale	<i>The calculation requires the structure (i.e., coordinates of all atoms) of a nanoparticle and input parameters (Buckingham and Coulomb force field parameterization) to calculate structural and energetic descriptors of the nanoparticle</i>

1	Aspect of the User Case/System to be Simulated	
1.1	Aspect of the User Case to be simulated	<i>Full-particle nano-descriptors calculated using molecular mechanics to evaluate the toxicity of different nanoparticles.</i>
1.2	Material	<i>Any material</i>
1.3	Geometry	<i>Spherical system ranging from nanometre to micrometre</i>
1.4	Time Lapse	<i>Not applicable</i>
1.5	Manufacturing process or in-service conditions	<i>Not applicable</i>

1.6	Publication on this data	<i>K. Tämm, L. Sikk, J. Burk, R. Rallo, S. Pokhrel, L. Mädler, J. J. Scott-Fordsmand, P. Burk, T. Tamm, Parametrization of nanoparticles: development of full-particle nanodescriptors, Nanoscale, 36, 2016, 16243-16250</i>
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2		Generic Physics of The Model Equation	
2.0	Model type and name	<i>Newton's equation based models – molecular mechanics based on empirical force fields</i>	
2.1	Model entity	<i>Atoms</i>	
2.2	Model Physics/ Chemistry equation PE	Equation	<i>Newton's equation of motions.</i>
		Physical quantities	<i>Coordinates and mass of each atom, interatomic potentials</i>
2.3	Materials relations	Relation	<i>Buckingham and Coulomb potential functions</i>
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<i>The Coulomb potential includes the partial charge of each atom and the dielectric constant of the medium where the material is located. The Buckingham potential includes atom pairs parameters (combination of two elements) and generic parameters such as the cut-off distance.</i>
2.4	Simulated input		

3		Solver and Computational translation of the specifications
3.1	Numerical Solver	<i>Energy minimization schemes (e.g., Polak-Ribiere version of the conjugate gradient algorithm) using Particle-Particle Particle-Mesh (PPPM) summation for long-range Coulomb potentials.</i>
3.2	Software tool	<i>LAMMPS, http://lammps.sandia.gov</i>
3.3	Time step	<i>Not applicable</i>

3.4	Computational Representation	Physics Equation, Material Relations, Material	<p><i>The Buckingham and Coulomb potentials are hardcoded as function of atoms type and position.</i></p> <p><i>Atoms are represented as material points.</i></p>
3.5	Computational boundary conditions	<i>Periodic boundary conditions expressing infinite domain</i>	
3.6	additional Solver Parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · <i>stopping tolerance for energy (10^{-4} unitless)</i> · <i>stopping tolerance for force (10^{-6} in eV/Angstrom)</i> · <i>max iterations of minimizer (100)</i> · <i>max number of force/energy evaluations (100000)</i> · <i>relative error in forces for the PPPM summation (10^{-5} unitless)</i> 	

4	POST PROCESSING		
4.1	The processed output	<p>The following descriptors are computed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total number of atoms in the NP - Total number of atoms residing in the core of the NP - Total number of atoms residing in the surface of the NP - For each chemical species, number of atoms of a particular species in the NP - For each chemical species, number of atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP - For each chemical, species, number of atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP - Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms in the NP - Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms residing in the core of the NP - Average per-atom potential energy for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP - For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species in the NP - For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP - For each chemical species, average per-atom potential energy for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP - Average HEX real part for all atoms in the NP - Average HEX real part for all atoms residing in the core of the NP - Average HEX real part for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP - For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species in the NP - For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP - For each chemical species, average HEX real part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP - Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms in the NP - Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms residing in the core of the NP 	

- Average HEX imaginary part for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average HEX imaginary part for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average CN for all atoms in the NP
- Average CN for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average CN for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average CN for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms in the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average PTM parameter for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP- For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average PTM parameter for all atoms of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms in the NP
- Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms residing in the NP core
- Average per-atom force vector length for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length for all atoms of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length for all atoms of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average per-atom force vector length of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms in the NP
- Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average normal component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP
- For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species in the NP
- For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the core of the NP
- For each chemical species, average normal component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP
- Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms in the NP
- Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the core of the NP
- Average tangential component of the per-atom force vector for all atoms residing in the surface of the NP

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For each chemical species, average tangential component of the force vector of a particular species in the NP - For each chemical species, average tangential component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the core of the NP - For each chemical species, average tangential component of the per-atom force vector of a particular species residing in the surface of the NP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NP diameter - NP surface area - NP volume - NP lattice energy - NP lattice energy per unit diameter - NP lattice energy per unit surface area - NP lattice energy per unit volume - Relative NP lattice energy to the lattice energy of the bulk material <p>where HEX for hexagonal order parameter, CN for coordination number and PTM for polyhedral template matching.</p>
4.2	Methodologies	<p>The per-atom potential energy is computed by summing all energetic contributions (pair, bond, angle, etc.) where the atom is part of. Each energy contribution is produced by a small set of atoms (e.g., 2 atoms in a bond or pair-wise interaction, 4 atoms in a dihedral or 3 atoms in a Tersoff 3-body interaction) and the energy is assigned in equal portions to each atom in the set, e.g., 1/4 of the dihedral energy to each of the 4 atoms and 1/2 of the bond energy in each of the two atoms.</p> <p>The hexagonal order parameter, ρ_i, of the i^{th} atom is a complex number defined as</p> $\rho_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \exp(i\theta_{ij})$ <p>where the sum is over the $N = 6$ nearest neighbours of the central i^{th} atom. The angle θ_{ij} is formed by the vector \vec{r}_{ij} and the x axis. ρ_i is calculated only using the x and y components, whereas the distance from the central atom is calculated using all three x, y, and z components of the bond vector. The complex number ρ_i is restricted to the unit disk of the complex plane i.e. $\rho_i \leq 1$.</p> <p>The coordination number of an atom counts the number of neighbour atoms (irrespective of atom type) that lie within a specified distance from the given atom. The distance is related to the ionic radii of the atoms in the NP; it is equal to 1.2 times of the maximum ionic radius of the species present in the NP.</p> <p>The PTM parameter of atom i is the square-root mean square deviation (RMSD) between its actual position and the position from its position in one of seven perfect lattices. The seven types of lattices are face-centred cubic, hexagonal close-packed, body-centred cubic, icosahedral, simple cubic, diamond cubic, diamond hexagonal, graphene. The identification of the ideal lattice is done employing the polyhedral template matching method.</p> <p>The per-atom force vector length is computed as $F_i = \sqrt{F_x^2 + F_y^2 + F_z^2}$ where \vec{F}_i is the per-atom force vector and x, y, z the three cartesian axes.</p> <p>The tangential component of the per-atom force vector is computed as $F_{t,i} = F_i \sin(\theta_i)$ where \vec{F}_i and $\vec{r}_{i,CM}$ position vectors of the i^{th} atom and the centre of mass of the NP. The normal component is computed as the difference between the per-atom force vector and the tangential component.</p>

		<p>The NP diameter is computed as twice the maximum distance of an atom from the centre of mass of the NP. The NP surface area and volume are calculated as $4\pi r^2$ and $\frac{4\pi r^3}{3}$ respectively, where r is the radius of a nanoparticle.</p> <p>The NP lattice energy is the product of the average per-atom potential energy with the number of atoms in the unit cell. The relative NP lattice energy to the lattice energy of the bulk material is the difference between the average per-atom potential energy of the bulk material and the average per-atom potential energy of the NP multiplied by the number of atoms in the unit cell structure.</p> <p>The parameters described in the sections above are spatially averaged in three ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Arithmetic average over all atoms belonging to the NP (ii) Arithmetic average over all atoms with a distance less than a given radius specified by the user from the centre-of-mass of the NP. This region corresponds to the “core” region of the NP (iii) Arithmetic average over all atoms which belong to the NP but not to the “core” <p>There is also averaging with respect to the chemical nature of the various species:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Arithmetic average over all atoms of the same chemical species (ii) Arithmetic average over all atoms irrespective of their chemical species
4.3	Margin Of Error	<i>Not applicable</i>